

Design and performance analysis of a low-cost monitoring system for advanced building envelopes

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to design a low-cost system for long-term monitoring of advanced building envelope and evaluates its performance in comparison to conventional lab-grade sensors. Leveraging the potential of a single-board computer and several low-cost digital sensors, the system measured thermo-physical and environmental parameters, including temperature, humidity, CO₂ levels, airflow rate, lighting, and heat flux. The system's architecture allowed for easy integration and flexible connectivity, providing comprehensive monitoring capabilities at a fraction of the cost of lab-grade systems. A basic prototype is available in a GitHub repository. The systematic evaluation of the proposed concept involved three key experiments using a double-skin façade mockup installed in a full-scale climate simulator. Sensor accuracy over 24 h was assessed through time-series comparison, showing high accuracy in recording air temperature, humidity, and surface temperature without on-site calibration, though calibration was essential for precise CO₂ and lighting measurements. Key performance indicators of the thermophysical behavior of envelope systems, such as U-value and g-value, were derived for both the low-cost and lab-grade setups. Discrepancies of up to 7 % in U-value and 13 % in g-value were observed, confirming the system's reliability for building energy assessments. Additionally, the low-cost system effectively represented dependencies between independent and dependent variables, as shown by analysis of variance, closely aligning with the picture obtained from lab-grade sensors' data. These findings validate the low-cost monitoring system as a viable, cost-effective alternative for advanced building envelope performance studies and indoor environmental quality assessments, highlighting the need for calibration of certain sensors.

1. Introduction

The evaluation and management of indoor environmental quality (IEQ) and energy performance in buildings greatly relies on effective monitoring systems [1] as only through accurate and comprehensive monitoring it is possible to characterize and optimizing the environmental conditions in buildings, which directly affect occupant comfort, health, and productivity [2]. However, accuracy and comprehensiveness oftentimes mean high complexity and high costs [3], a constraint that limits the widespread adoption of monitoring systems. This limitation is even more evident in the case of complex and advanced building envelope technologies (such as, for example, double-skin façade (DSF) [4]), where a rather large range of physical quantities should be monitored to have a comprehensive picture in real-time about

the ongoing phenomena.

Traditionally, monitoring systems have evolved from laboratory grade instrumentation, and their scalability in terms of number and widespread adoption is therefore limited, especially for extensive research projects or large-scale implementations [5]. The final effect is that (high cost) monitoring systems are typically designed for short-term, spot measurements, carried out for limited time periods and in limited areas or on just few components. This approach is inadequate for comprehensive IEQ assessment, given the inherent spatial and temporal heterogeneity of IEQ parameters within buildings [6]. Long-term monitoring is essential to accurately capture this variability, a need that current high-cost solutions fail to meet.

In response to these challenges, the development of affordable monitoring systems is gaining increasing interest [7–10]. These systems are based on the use of rather inexpensive, digital sensors that derive

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Nomenclature

Parameters

a	Coefficient for airflow calculation
b	Exponent for airflow calculation
c_p	Specific heat capacity
g	Solar heat gain coefficient (g-value)
I_{in}	Direct transmitted irradiance
I_{out}	Global solar irradiance impinging on the vertical plane
p-value	Probability value indicating the significance of results
Q_g	Total transmitted solar flux through the glazed surface
Q_{HFM}	Heat flux meter readings
Q_{net}	Net heat flux through window
Q_{vent}	Normalized heat gain/loss rate by airflow passing through cavity
Q_c	Airflow rate through cavity
SS_f	Sum of squares for the factor
SS_T	Total sum of squares
$T_{s,in}$	Indoor surface temperature of glazing
T_{in}	Indoor air temperature
T_{inlet}	Cavity inlet air temperature
T_{out}	Outdoor air temperature
T_{outlet}	Cavity outlet air temperature
U	Heat transfer coefficient (U-value)
A_{win}	Window surface area

Greek Symbols

ΔT	Temperature difference between outdoor and indoor air
ΔP	Pressure drop through the air opening
ρ	Air density
η^2	Contribution parameter (eta squared)

Subscripts

c	Referred to cavity
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g	Referred to the glazed surface
HFM	Referred to heat flux meter
in	Referred to indoor
inlet	Referred to cavity's inlet air
j	Referred to summation index
net	Referred to net value
out	Referred to outdoor
outlet	Referred to cavity's outlet air
s	Referred to surface of glazing
vent	Referred to ventilation through cavity
win	Referred to window

Abbreviations

ADC	Analog-to-digital converter
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
EcoDAQ	Economical data acquisition
DoE	Design of experiments
DSF	Double-skin façade
I ² C	Inter-integrated circuit
IAC	Indoor air curtain
IEQ	Indoor environmental quality
KPI	Key performance indicator
MAD	Mean absolute deviation
OAC	Outdoor air curtain
OH	Opening height
RPi	Raspberry Pi
RMSE	Root mean squared error
SBC	Single-board computers
SI	Solar irradiation
TB	Thermal buffer
FS	Fan speed

from robotics or hobbyist applications, combined with multipurpose, single-board computers (SBCs). The pricing of low-cost environmental monitoring sensors and devices can differ significantly due to various factors. These include the type of the environmental parameter being monitored (e.g., temperature, humidity, air quality), the sensors' accuracy and reliability, the connectivity options (e.g., wire, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi), and the presence of supplementary functionalities or integrated data analysis capabilities on the device. Karagulian et al. [11] conducted an exhaustive review of 64 studies associated with air quality monitoring, revealing an extensive price range for low-cost sensors and devices ranging from 10 to 10,000 €. In addition to a reduction in the cost of the whole system, such alternative monitoring concept provides additional advantages in the form of simplified installation processes, flexible transmission capabilities, variable time-interval recording options, and simpler data extraction processes [12,13].

The use of RPi [14–17] as a single-board computer (SBC), Arduino [18–21] as a microcontroller platform, along with other comparable devices [22–25] has gained increasing popularity in recent years in the field of environmental monitoring. These systems offer a platform for integrating a diverse range of sensors and modules, enabling comprehensive monitoring of various environmental factors through a singular, efficient system. The appeal of these platforms, particularly RPi and Arduino, lies in their open-source nature, affordability, and user-friendliness, making them accessible to a wide array of users. For instance, the cost of a RPi varies significantly based on the model, ranging from approximately 20 to 75 €, at the time of the development of the system. This price variation spans from the more economical RPi Zero W to the higher-end RPi 5B model.

In order to collect indoor environmental data from twelve pre-existing buildings, Anik et al. [26] employed a network of RPi-based sensors. This setup included sensor modules for monitoring temperature, humidity, light, sound, flame, vibration, motion, smoke, carbon monoxide, and liquefied petroleum gas. In a similar vein, Luna-Navarro et al. [27] explored the impact of façades on IEQ and occupant reactions using an IoT system based on RPi. Their study demonstrated the system's capability to non-intrusively monitor occupant comfort and interaction with the façade, effectively capturing the façade's influence on IEQ over time and space. Moreover, Karami et al. [28] investigated IEQ through a low-cost, portable toolbox equipped with sensors for occupancy, temperature, humidity, illuminance, CO₂, VOC, and PM_{2.5}. Utilizing an Arduino board for data collection, their study validated the system's reliability and robustness through continuous monitoring in the open computer lab of a commercial building.

When it comes to low-cost sensors, well-known commercial monitoring systems such as Airthings, AirVisual, Awair, Clarity, Foobot, Kaiterra, Temtop and uHoo rely heavily on these affordable technologies. These devices are praised for their accessibility, affordability, and real-time monitoring capabilities, which have made them popular in both residential and commercial settings. However, these systems have notable limitations, particularly in terms of reliability, data quality, and flexibility. Many manufacturers offer limited transparency regarding the specific sensors employed, leading to uncertainties about measurement accuracy and consistency. Additionally, these systems often lack the versatility needed to monitor a comprehensive range of environmental parameters, reducing their suitability for experimental research and detailed performance evaluations. Some devices rely on indirect

measurement methods; for example, Foobot estimates CO₂ concentrations based on VOC readings rather than using dedicated sensors, resulting in significant inaccuracies [29]. Furthermore, deSouza [30] identified prevalent concerns among users of 94 different commercial low-cost air quality monitoring systems, including issues related to sensor accuracy, operational reliability (such as battery life and connectivity), and overall data trustworthiness.

Despite the advancements in low-cost monitoring technologies, the accuracy, reliability, and overall practicality of these sensors remain areas of concern. These limitations are largely due to the fact that both the sensors and SBC devices were not originally designed to meet the stringent data collection standards typically expected in laboratory settings. Furthermore, the existing literature does not provide extensive validation of low-cost monitoring systems, with most studies raising concerns about data quality. To fill this gap, we designed this study to investigate a low-cost monitoring system through a systematic experimental approach involving three steps: raw data evaluation, processed data evaluation, and key performance indicators (KPIs) assessment in connection with independent variables.

To contribute to the development of low-cost monitoring possibilities, and the verification of such concept, we have designed and tested an economical data acquisition (EcoDAQ) system with advanced monitoring capabilities. The goal of the EcoDAQ is to enable long-term data acquisition at a fraction, approximately one tenth of the cost of a laboratory grade system, with a data quality and monitoring reliability that target as much as possible the level of a laboratory grade system. Based on the available literature, there is a scarcity of studies that have conducted a systematic evaluation of the reliability of such monitoring systems. In particular, it is interesting to understand whether or not such alternative data acquisition approach can deliver a good match at both the level of reading of the individual physical quantity, as well as at the level of characterization of relevant key performance indicators (KPIs). In this study, we therefore seek to address key research questions:

- How can the EcoDAQ system capable of monitoring the performance of advanced building envelopes be developed?
- Can the EcoDAQ system achieve the desired level of accuracy and sensitivity necessary for accurate and reliable monitoring?

The significance of this research lies in its potential to facilitate access to advanced monitoring capabilities for building envelope performance and IEQ assessments, overcoming economic [31] and complexity [3] constraints that have traditionally limited the scope of long-term monitoring, in both the field of advanced building envelope systems and in adjacent fields more openly linked to IEQ and energy use in buildings. The relevance of this study extends to institutions, researchers, and professionals involved in building performance and environment assessment by providing a cost-effective, accurate, and adaptable solution that expands the scope of the comprehensive experimental investigation.

We tackled this problem by developing the DAQ system that is not only cost-effective because it employs inexpensive embedded digital and, where digital are unavailable, analog sensors and a low-cost Raspberry Pi (RPI) minicomputer, which is also flexible and comprehensive, allowing for the monitoring of the most essential and widely used environmental variables. In conjunction with data recording, the practice of storing data in the cloud is formed, facilitating real-time data monitoring and analysis. When it comes to the assessment and verification process, the effectiveness of the designed monitoring system was evaluated by means of comparison with a laboratory grade system, utilizing a full-scale mock-up of an advanced building envelope system, installed in a climate simulator, where a broad set of tests carried were carried out.

The subsequent sections of this work are outlined as follows. In the methodology session, we provide comprehensive information about the architecture of the EcoDAQ system, the experimental setup, the design

of the experiments, as well as the data processing methods and analysis. In the results and discussion session, we present the comparison between data collection through the EcoDAQ and the lab-grade system, showing their accuracy in measuring both fundamental physical quantities and determining KPI values under a large variation of boundary conditions. Finally, in the Conclusion section, the primary insights gained from this research work are summarized.

2. Methodology

The methodology for this study is structured to systematically develop, implement, and evaluate the EcoDAQ system for monitoring advanced building envelope performance and indoor environmental quality (IEQ) parameters. The experimental process was carefully designed to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the system's capabilities, from hardware integration to data processing and KPI assessment. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the experimental methodology, summarizing the key steps involved in the study. This flowchart outlines the design and development of the EcoDAQ system, the setup of the experimental environment, and the detailed procedures for data collection, processing, and analysis. Each stage of the methodology is described in detail in the following sections, highlighting the specific tasks and approaches used to achieve the research objectives.

2.1. Design of the EcoDAQ system

The proposed EcoDAQ system in this work employs as a RPi 4. SBCs like the RPi are valued for their simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and low power consumption, making them ideal for embedded applications and long-term monitoring. Additionally, it provides sufficient computing power and ample connectivity options, making it suitable for a wide range of data acquisition applications. The availability of a robust software ecosystem and community support further enhances its usability and expandability. The SBC has the function to pull data information from the digital sensors, process it, and store that on cloud-based data storage solution. From there, data can be easily accessed and post-processed outside the DAQ physical devices. In Fig. 2, the DAQ architecture is depicted. In hardware part, various types of low-cost sensors are connected to RPi with wires. The software layer is set up to manage data reception by the RPi, transfer it to InfluxDB, and prepare it for visualization using Grafana.

The RPi 4 supports the I²C (Inter-integrated Circuit) protocol, enabling straightforward data exchange and powering of digital sensors (Fig. 3). I²C uses a 2-wire, bidirectional channel to connect the RPi 4 (master) with multiple sensors (slaves) without requiring complex wiring or additional devices. This simple topology can theoretically support up to 112 devices, sufficient for most environmental and energy monitoring needs. Sensors are identified by unique addresses on the I²C bus, but address conflicts can occur if multiple sensors share the same default address. To resolve this, multiplexers can be used, allowing multiple sensors with the same address to connect to the same I²C line by dynamically routing signals. The current system can handle up to 8 multiplexers on one bus line.

Significant cost savings in the EcoDAQ system are achieved by using inexpensive digital sensors. However, some measurements, like heat-flux, require reliable analog sensors. These sensors can be integrated using analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) on the I²C bus, allowing the system to accommodate both digital and analog inputs. Each I²C line can support up to 180 sensors using 8 multiplexers and 4 ADCs, including both direct connections and those routed through multiplexers. While the EcoDAQ system can theoretically manage up to 360 sensors across two I²C lines, practical constraints such as address conflicts, power consumption, and signal integrity typically reduce the actual number of feasible connections to well below this maximum. In this experiment, 32 digital and analog sensors (the latter with ADCs) are connected through I²C to the EcoDAQ system, with details provided in the experimental

Fig. 1. Overview of the experimental methodology for EcoDAQ system development and evaluation.

setup section. In addition to cost, key considerations for sensor selection in the EcoDAQ system included accuracy, range, resolution, power supply voltage, output type (analog or digital), and compatibility with the I²C interface protocol.

The software architecture of the EcoDAQ system is crucial for efficient data handling and visualization. The system employs a software stack comprising Docker, Python, InfluxDB, and Grafana. Docker is used to containerize the application, ensuring consistent and reliable performance across different deployment environments, while also enhancing portability and ease of management. Python serves as the primary programming language, facilitating interaction between the RPi and the connected digital sensors via the I²C communication protocol. Python scripts manage data acquisition and transmitting it to InfluxDB, a high-performance time-series database optimized for storing large volumes of timestamped environmental data. For data visualization, Grafana is employed, offering a user-friendly interface for creating real-time dashboards. These dashboards allow for immediate detection of anomalies and trends, which enhances decision-making, improves safety, reduces risks, and leads to cost savings. The combination of Docker, Python, InfluxDB, and Grafana ensures seamless data flow from sensors to visualization, providing scalability and flexibility for future expansions of the EcoDAQ system. A basic prototype of the DAQ system is available in a GitHub repository [33] for public access and further development. The repository includes all the necessary steps and detailed instructions for setting up the software, ensuring a seamless implementation of the system.

2.2. Experimental setup

A climate simulator available at the joint laboratory of NTNU and SINTEF community in Trondheim, Norway, has been used to provide several variable boundary conditions to test the reliability of the designed low-cost monitoring system. This full-scale experimental facility can replicate a wide range of climatic variables such as air temperature, humidity, precipitation, incident solar radiation, and pressure differentials. The facility is made of a two-chamber system (where in one a full-scale solar simulator is installed) and a removable frame, placed between the two chambers, where building envelope systems can be mounted for testing. In this specific case, a previously developed flexible DSF prototype has been used as advanced building envelope test sample [31]. DSF is generally a complex façade system comprising two layers of glass separated by an air gap [34]. This design is known for its enhanced thermal [35] and acoustic [36] properties, contributing to a building's natural ventilation [37] and energy efficiency [38]. This façade system, which already integrated a comprehensive laboratory grade DAQ system, has been equipped with the proposed EcoDAQ system with 32 low-cost sensors, with the majority priced between 5 and 30 € each. Figs. 4 and 5 provide a detailed overview of the experimental setup in the SINTEF climate simulator. The layout of sensors used in the experiments, along with information about their models, accuracy, and quantity are illustrated.

Focusing on the sensor costs used in this experiment, the lab-grade DAQ system is significantly more expensive compared to the low-cost EcoDAQ system. The use of more expensive sensors, such as the

Fig. 2. The EcoDAQ system architecture.

HFP01 heat flux sensor, contributes notably to this difference. If heat flux monitoring is not required, or if affordable alternatives for heat flux sensors become available, the cost gap between the two systems would widen further, with the EcoDAQ system potentially being 10 times more cost-effective than the lab-grade system. Current heat flux meters on the market, such as the FluxTeq PHFS-01, EKO HF-10S, and Hukseflux HFP01, are typically priced between 200 and 300 euros, underscoring

the importance of future research and development aimed at producing more affordable alternatives, which could make low-cost data acquisition systems like EcoDAQ even more accessible.

It is important to note that this cost analysis focuses primarily on sensor costs. A complete monitoring system also requires a computer for data acquisition. The RPi used in the EcoDAQ system costs around 150 euros (including necessary components like connections and a monitor), whereas lab-grade DAQ systems typically involve much higher costs for equivalent computational power. Taking into account the computer cost, the price difference between the two systems could increase to over 20 times in favor of the EcoDAQ system.

In this study, three separated experimental activities have conducted to thoroughly evaluate the performance of a low-cost monitoring system. These phases include: (1) time-series comparison for a number of key thermophysical quantities, (2) U-value and g-value determination based on data postprocessing, and (3) assessment of DSF's performance indicators which is used to identify the relevant factors in DSF operations, following the approach adopted in a previous study [39]. In these experiments, three different operational modes of DSF were utilized: thermal buffer (TB), indoor air curtain (IAC), and outdoor air curtain (OAC). TB mode involves using a thermal buffer to moderate temperature fluctuations within the DSF, with all openings on both the inside and outside closed. IAC mode employs an air curtain inside the DSF to control indoor air temperature, with indoor openings open to circulate air from inside the building to the cavity. OAC mode uses an air curtain on the exterior of the DSF to influence its thermal performance, with outdoor openings open to circulate outdoor air with the cavity air. The goal of this arrangement is to reduce solar gain through the glazing.

2.2.1. Experiment A: time-series comparison

The initial phase involved a 24 h measurement under cold conditions, with outdoor temperatures ranging from 5 to 15 °C and solar radiation peaking at 400 W/m². The indoor temperature was consistently maintained at 25 °C. All experimental parameters for this test are listed in Table 1. This experiment aimed to assess the operational precision of the low-cost sensors in comparison to lab-grade sensors, focusing on key

Fig. 3. The EcoDAQ system based on RPi. The protocol I²C was created to allow communication between one or more controllers and many slave-integrated circuits. The serial data line (SDA) and serial clock line (SCL) are bidirectional open-drain lines pushed up by resistors [32]. A bidirectional SDA channel transfers data between master and slave devices. This line transmits and receives data in both ways. The master device controls unidirectional SCL data transfer and timed SDA data transmission.

Sensor	Low-cost sensor		Symbol	Installation position							Total quantity	Lab-grade sensor	
	Model	Accuracy (sensing range)		outside	outer-outer	outer-inner	cavity	inner-outer	inner-inner	inside		Model	Accuracy (sensing range)
Air temperature and humidity	BME280	±1.0 °C ±2% RH	1	1						1	2	DeltaOhm (HD48S17TV)	±0.3 °C (0 to 70°C) ±1.5 %RH (0 to 90 %RH)
Air temperature and humidity	SHT31D	±0.2 °C ±2% RH	2	1						1	2		
Air temperature, humidity, CO ₂	SCD30	>±0.4 °C ±3% RH ±30 ppm +3%	3	1						1	2	DeltaOhm (HD37BTC)	±50 ppm +3% (0 to 2000 ppm)
Illuminance	TSL2591	(0 to 88K+ lux)	4	1							2		
Illuminance	SI1145	(0 to 128K lux)	5	1							2	Pyranometer DeltaOhm (LPPYRA03ACM12)	Second class Pyranometer (ISO 9060)
Illuminance	BH1750	(0 to 65K+ lux)	6	1							2		
Air/glazing surface temperature	MCP9808	±0.25°C	7	1	1	10	1	1			14	DeltaOhm (HD4807TC1.5)	±0.3 °C (0 to 70°C)
Glazing surface temperature	TMP117	±0.2°C	8	1						1	2	Sterling Sensors Pt100	Class B (IEC 60751:2008)
Heat flux plate	HFP01	<±3% of reading	9	1							2	Hukseflux (HFP01)	<±3% of reading
Differential pressure	SDP810-125Pa	3% of reading (-125 to 125 Pa)	10			1					1	Hot-wire anemometers DeltaOhm (HD2937TC1.5)	± 0.1 m/s + 3% (0 to 1 m/s)
Differential pressure	SDP610-25Pa	3% of reading (-25 to + 25 Pa)	11			1					1		

Fig. 4. Sensor layout in the SINTEF climate simulator. Sensors labeled 1, 2, and 3 record indoor and outdoor air properties. Sensors 4–9 installed on the glazing surface, and multiple sensors 7 for cavity air temperature. Sensors 10 and 11 measure air pressure drop at the opening.

Fig. 5. The EcoDAQ and lab-grade systems in SINTEF climate simulator. The top image (a) shows the external view of the climate simulator, featuring the two-room system and the frame in between. The bottom images (b) depict both the EcoDAQ and lab-grade systems, including sensor positioning, wiring, and monitoring controllers. The lower left and middle images focus on the sensors, while the lower left image also shows the main boards of both systems.

environmental factors such as indoor and outdoor temperatures, humidity, CO₂ concentrations, and radiation levels. The collected data was used for understanding the monitoring system’s response and analyzing the thermal behavior of the window unit in dynamic environmental

conditions.

2.2.2. Experiment B: U-value and g-value calculations

Subsequent experiments, the second phase, focused on U-value and

Table 1
Experimental parameters for the experiment A.

Test order	Outdoor temperature (°C)	Indoor temperature (°C)	Solar irradiance (W/m ²)	Opening height (cm)	Fan speed (%)	Operation mode
1	5 to 15	25	0 to 400	5	20	IAC

g-value of DSF. The U-value, which shows heat transfer due to thermal gradient across the transparent part of the DSF, and the solar heat gain coefficient (g-value), which shows the total solar energy transmission through the transparent part of the DSF [40], are two of the most important thermal properties of a DSF. This study specifically examines the U-value of the glazed part, excluding the frame sections. This choice is justified by the significantly larger role that the glazed area has in determining the global performance of a predominantly glazed façade. The reliability of a low-cost monitoring system in computing these essential characteristics is gauged against data obtained from lab-grade sensors. If the low-cost system's readings align with those from the lab-grade sensors, it may serve as a viable, cost-effective option for similar studies moving forward. Substantial discrepancies, however, would prompt a reassessment of the low-cost system's role in precision-critical applications.

The parameters U and g are determined through linear regression using the well-known Ordinary Least Squares method, with the condition that the dependent variable is zero when the independent variable is zero [41]. For the U-value, which quantifies the thermal transmittance of the façade, the experiments were conducted in accordance with ISO 9869-1 standards [42] that recommend steady-state conditions by the use of a hot and a cold box (climate simulator), devoid of solar irradiance. U-value is achieved by directly correlating the heat-flux meter readings (q_{HFM}) with the temperature difference between the measured outdoor and indoor air temperatures (ΔT), as described in Eqs. (1) and (2) [41].

$$\bar{U} = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta T_j \cdot q_{\text{HFM},j} \right) / \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta T_j^2 \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta T = T_{\text{out}} - T_{\text{in}} \quad (2)$$

For calculating the g-value, which measures the façade's efficiency in transmitting solar energy, the experiments incorporate lighting sensors to record incident and transmitted solar radiation. Similarly, the equivalent solar factor g is assessed using only day-time readings. This assessment involves a linear regression, as described in Eqs. (3) and (4), correlating the total transmitted solar flux (q_g) with the global solar irradiance impinging on the vertical plane (I_{out}), which defines the value of g [41].

$$\bar{g} = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n I_{\text{out},j} \cdot q_{g,j} \right) / \left(\sum_{j=1}^n I_{\text{out},j}^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

$$q_g = I_{\text{in}} + (q_{\text{HFM}} - \bar{U} \cdot \Delta T) \quad (4)$$

where the total transmitted solar flux (q_g) is the sum of direct transmitted irradiance (I_{in}) and secondary transmitted flux (shown in parentheses). To better understand the second component, consider that the heat flux meter captures two types of heat flux: heat flux released at the indoor interface because of the thermal gradient between outside and inside, and heat flux released towards the inside because of secondary transmittance. More detail are available in reference [41]. In this experiment, I_{out} and I_{in} were measured by both pyranometers and calibrated low-cost lighting sensors.

A total of four experiments were conducted to evaluate the reliability of a low-cost monitoring system in comparison to a laboratory-grade system, with a focus on the characterization of two typical performance indicators for standard building envelope components: U-value and g-value. For U-value characterization, the experiment was conducted under controlled conditions, with the outdoor air temperature set to 0 °C, the indoor air temperature to 20 °C, and the outdoor solar irradiance to 0 W/m². These conditions were chosen to ensure a high temperature difference between the inside and outside, while avoiding solar irradiance, in accordance with the ISO 9869-1 standard. It was done under TB operational mode. For g-value evaluation, three

experiments were conducted. These experiments maintained consistent environmental conditions, with the outdoor air temperature at 30 °C, indoor air temperature at 25 °C, and outdoor solar irradiance at 500 W/m². The experiments differed based on the operational modes: one used TB mode, another used IAC mode, and the third used OAC mode. All experimental parameters for this test are presented in Table 2.

2.2.3. Experiment C: KPI analysis for DSFs

The final phase of the experiments aimed to investigate the reliability of the EcoDAQ system in assessing KPIs for the DSF. This phase evaluated the DSF's thermal behavior and efficiency in different environmental scenarios, focusing on the ability of the EcoDAQ system to depict dependencies between independent and dependent variables. The key aspect of this comparison was to verify if performing an ANOVA with lab-grade data versus low-cost data would yield the same results. This assessment included analyzing not just single readings (as in experiment A) or single data processing instances (as in experiment B), but the system's overall capability to accurately represent the relationship between variables.

To have a both a detailed DSF evaluation and a large range of variations in the different boundary and operational conditions, a design of experiments (DoE) method was used. In this way, a coherent group of experiments was created, allowing statistical-based analysis on the influence of independent parameters on the KPIs (the dependent variables) of the DSF. DoE is a methodical and efficient procedure for organizing and performing experiments to discover and comprehend the relationship between a system's input variables (factors) and its output response or reactions [43]. This method helps researchers to decrease the quantity of trials needed to establish the characteristics of a system while simultaneously enhancing the informational value derived from the experimental data [44]. While there exist multiple DoE techniques, the definitive screening design was chosen for this study due to its ability to reconcile resource requirements (i.e., the number of experimental runs) with the capability of evaluating response curvature caused by higher order terms. In previous publications [39,43], a similar style of design was utilized to successfully describe a system similar to the one under consideration.

Thirteen experiments were designed using the DoE technique, with four factors, including the temperature difference between inside and outside (ΔT), solar irradiance (SI) on the vertical plane outdoors, air opening height (OH), and fan speed (FS). These independent variables (factors) with multiple levels for all designed experiments are listed in Table 3.

These experiments were designed to check impact of the factors on DSF's KPIs such as inside glazing surface temperature, $T_{s,\text{in}}$ (KPI₁), airflow rate inside the cavity, Q_c (KPI₂), heat gain/loss rate by the airflow passing through the cavity normalized by the DSF surface, q_{vent} (KPI₃), and net heat flux passing through the window toward the inside, q_{net} (KPI₄). The quantitative representation of these indicators is provided through the following equations:

$$\text{KPI}_1 \rightarrow T_{s,\text{in}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{KPI}_2 \rightarrow Q_c = a(\Delta P)^b \quad (6)$$

$$\text{KPI}_3 \rightarrow q_{\text{vent}} = \rho Q_c c_p (T_{\text{outlet}} - T_{\text{inlet}}) / A_{\text{win}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{KPI}_4 \rightarrow q_{\text{net}} = q_{\text{HFM}} + I_{\text{in}} \quad (8)$$

where ΔP is pressure drop through the air opening, a and b are coefficients, ρ and c_p are air density and specific heat capacity, T_{outlet} and T_{inlet} denote the cavity's outlet and inlet air temperature, A_{win} refers to the window surface area, q_{HFM} is the heat flux density passing through the façade by heat flux meter to the interior, and I_{in} is direct transmitted incident solar radiation.

Table 2
Experimental parameters for the experiment B.

Test order	Outdoor temperature (°C)	Indoor temperature (°C)	Solar irradiance (W/m ²)	Opening height (cm)	Fan speed (%)	Operation mode
1	0	20	0	5	0	TB
2	30	25	500	5	0	TB
3	30	25	500	5	30	IAC
4	30	25	500	5	30	OAC

Table 3
Experimental parameters for the experiment C.

Test order	Outdoor temperature (°C)	Indoor temperature (°C)	Solar irradiance (W/m ²)	Opening height (cm)	Fan speed (%)	Operation mode
1	15	25	400	5	30	OAC
2	15	25	800	5	20	OAC
3	25	25	0	5	10	OAC
4	35	25	0	5	30	OAC
5	35	25	800	5	10	OAC
6	15	25	0	15	10	OAC
7	25	25	400	15	20	OAC
8	35	25	800	15	30	OAC
9	15	25	0	30	30	OAC
10	15	25	800	30	10	OAC
11	25	25	800	30	30	OAC
12	35	25	400	30	10	OAC
13	35	25	0	30	20	OAC

2.3. Data processing techniques and analysis

2.3.1. Data processing

For the experiment A, which is a time-series comparison between datasets from low-cost and lab-grade sensors, both datasets were recorded over a 24 h period at one-minute intervals. The initial step involved time alignment and resampling. Timestamps of both datasets were aligned, and data was resampled to a uniform time interval of every five minutes. This was crucial for synchronizing the datasets, facilitating a direct and accurate comparison. Additionally, the challenge of differing measurement units, particularly for the lighting sensors, was addressed. The pyranometers recorded values in W/m², while the low-cost sensors provided readings in Lux. To standardize these measurements, a conversion factor from the literature was used, stating that solar irradiance of 1 Sun (1000 W/m²) is approximately equivalent to 120,000 Lux [45], although this conversion factor depends on the type of sky and should likely be subject to calibration at a later stage.

For the experiment B and C, data from both low-cost and lab-grade sensors were recorded over a 4 h period at one-minute intervals. Since measurements conducted in a controlled environmental condition (independent factors including ΔT , SI, FS, and OH were maintained constant), it took time for the climate simulator to reach steady-state conditions. Therefore, the datasets from the four experiments for U-value and g-value calculation, and the 13 experiments for detailed DSF characterization were filtered to include only a 1 h period after steady state conditions were reached.

2.3.2. Data analysis

In experiment A, a time series analysis was conducted to observe trends, periodicity, and patterns over a 24 h period. This included comparing sensor readings throughout the day. In cases of significant deviation in low-cost sensor readings from reference values, regression techniques were applied to model the relationship between the datasets. For experiment B, the focus was on calculating the relative error for U-value and g-value. In Experiment C, the mean absolute deviation (MAD) was calculated for each KPI. These metrics helped quantify the differences in readings and calculations between the two sensor sets.

Further, in experiment C, analysis of variance (ANOVA), was employed. This was utilized to test the differences between two or more means and to determine how certain independent factors influenced

critical DSF indicators. The objective is to compare ANOVA results obtained from the indicators calculated using both lab-grade and low-cost sensors, assessing the performance of the developed EcoDAQ system.

Factorial ANOVA (multi-way ANOVA) was used to examine the main effects and interactions of independent factors on the dependent variable in the presence of multiple categorical factors. The contribution parameter ($\eta^2 = SS_f/SS_T$) [46], which represents the proportion of variance in an outcome variable explained by an independent variable, was also calculated. A higher η^2 value indicates a larger impact of that factor on the variability of the response variable [47]. Additionally, the p-value in the ANOVA table was closely examined. The p-values, especially those lower than 0.05, indicate the statistical significance of the factor in contributing to the observed variation in the response variable [48].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Time-series comparison

This section presents the results of experiment A, which evaluates the precision and reliability of the EcoDAQ system compared to lab-grade sensors. The experiment focuses on measuring key environmental factors, including indoor and outdoor temperatures, humidity, CO₂ concentrations, heat flux rate and radiation levels.

Fig. 6 demonstrates how low-cost sensors perform in relation to lab-grade counterparts across a range of environmental conditions obtained in the climate simulator. The results indicate that low-cost sensors such as the SHT31-D and BME280 for temperature and humidity measurements trace the reference sensors closely, suggesting that these sensors can be trusted for accurate data collection without the need for individual calibration. This finding is pivotal, as it suggests that for temperature and humidity, the deployment of low-cost sensors can be both cost-effective and scientifically robust.

The performance of the MCP9808 sensor exhibited an increase in measurement error when placed at upper level within the cavity, signaling the need for a thorough review of its accuracy throughout its entire operational range. This observed error was attributed to an unintentional connection of the upper sensor (inner cavity) to the window frame. Nevertheless, the general performance of the MCP9808 sensors, in terms of air and surface temperature measurements, stayed within a

Fig. 6. Time-series measurement comparison between the EcoDAQ and lab-grade system.

permissible margin of error, endorsing their suitability for such applications.

The SCD30 sensor, typically employed for CO₂ monitoring, also measures temperature and relative humidity. The data indicates that the CO₂ concentration measurements have a substantial deviation from those of the reference sensor, with around 90 ppm deviation which is nearly triple its specified accuracy range. Furthermore, the sensor shows higher variation for temperature and relative humidity in comparison to other low-cost sensors. These findings suggest that deploying the SCD30 sensor without appropriate calibration could result in notable discrepancies, underscoring the importance of calibration to ensure the accuracy of the readings.

When measuring surface temperatures, the MCP9808 and TMP117 showed excellent agreement in outside temperatures, although the MCP9808 sensor deviation grew slightly as the temperature rose. It implies that additional testing is necessary to determine its dependability. To enhance the precision of these measurements, both sensors were affixed to surfaces using thermal paste and shielded by an aluminum cover to protect them from direct solar radiation. The aluminum shield is not directly connected to the sensors; it serves only to protect them from direct light exposure. For surface-mounted sensors, a layer of duct tape separates the sensor from the shield, while an air gap is maintained for sensors measuring ambient air to prevent any interference with the measurements. Ensuring that these measures are correctly implemented is crucial, as any deviation from this setup could introduce errors in the readings.

In this study, both the low-cost and lab-grade monitoring systems utilized the HFP01 sensor, a moderately priced option, for measuring heat flux. To enable precise tracking of low-range heat flux density through the building envelope, the lab-grade system incorporated two heat flux meters installed in close proximity and connected in series on either side of the window. The analysis reveals that heat flux sensor, when interfaced with the RPi using the I²C protocol, delivers nearly equivalent measurements compared to the serially connected sensors in the lab-grade setup. This observation is especially significant in the inside glazing, where heat flux rate is very low.

In assessing the performance of lighting sensors, notable discrepancies emerge when comparing the readings from low-cost sensors to those from the reference Pyranometer. Low-cost lighting sensors capture non-unit values, and they can be configured for different gain/timing ranges to detect different light ranges. This configuration should be done in the Python script. Given the significant discrepancies between low-cost and reference lighting sensors that are shown in Fig. 6, it appears essential to calibrate them prior to use.

Fig. 7 presents a detailed linear regression analysis comparing irradiance levels measured by the low-cost sensors and the reference

Pyranometer under both indoor and outdoor conditions. The regression models, based on several days of steady-state data, cover a wide range of solar radiation from 0 to 800 W/m². These models aim to establish a clear correlation between the datasets from the low-cost sensors and the reference sensor. The solid blue, green, and red lines in the figure represent linear regression fits for the TSL2591, BH1750, and SI1145 sensors, respectively, across both indoor and outdoor environments. These lines illustrate the relationship between irradiance levels recorded by the EcoDAQ system (x-axis) and the lab-grade DAQ system (y-axis). The high R² values indicate a strong correlation between the two, suggesting that low-cost sensors can reliably track irradiance levels when appropriate conversion factors are applied. This demonstrates the potential of these low-cost sensors for accurately monitoring lighting conditions.

3.2. U-value and g-value calculations

This section details the findings from experiment B, which focused on calculating the U-value and g-value of the DSF. The results for the U-value and g-value are presented in Table 4. Calculated U-value based on the low-cost system's measurements closely align with those from the lab-grade sensors, with discrepancies as maximum as around 7% when using the SCD30 sensor.

The acceptable error margin for g-value obtained from the low-cost sensors does not exceed 13 %, which is within a permissible range for practical applications. These results are based on lighting measurements calibrated by regression models shown in Fig. 7, which confirms the potential of calibrated low-cost sensors to accurately assess key characteristics of DSF systems. The obtained g-values aligned with expectations, showcasing variations among different configurations. For instance, the IAC was anticipated to reduce heat transfer toward the indoor environment due to an expected decrease in temperature difference between the interior and exterior glazing, resulting in a lower g-value. Similarly, to a lesser extent, this is caused by a decrease in the long-wave radiation emitted from the inner glazing, considering an expected reduction in its temperature. For the OAC mode, we expect the opposite thing, as the hot air should amplify heat transmission through glazing toward the indoor environment and long-wave irradiation from the indoor glazing due to its elevated temperature.

It is important to highlight that the U-value determinations presented herein are derived from factory-calibrated sensor recordings, demonstrating the low-cost system's precision. In contrast, the g-values are based on data from on-site calibrated lighting sensors, acknowledging that such sensors require calibration to produce valid results. This distinction underscores a point: while low-cost sensors can often produce reliable data with factory-calibration, certain parameters

Fig. 7. Regression analysis of indoor and outdoor lighting sensors. TSL2591, BH1750, and SI1145 are low-cost sensors with technical details provided in Fig. 4.

Table 4
Experiment design to calculate the U-value and g-value using EcoDAQ and lab-grade DAQ system.

Test order	Test conditions					Sensor type	U-value / g-value		
	Outdoor temp (°C)	Indoor temp (°C)	Solar irradiance (W/m ²)	Fan speed (%)	Operation mode		EcoDAQ	Lab-grade DAQ	Error (%)
1	0	20	0	0	TB	SHT31-D	U-value		3.7
						BME280	0.56	0.54	1.9
						SCD30	0.55		7.4
2	30	25	500	0	TB	TSL2591	g-value		3.9
						BH1750	0.28	0.26	7.6
						SI1145	0.29		3.9
3	30	25	500	30%	IAC	TSL2591			4.2
						BH1750	0.25	0.24	8.3
						SI1145	0.26		12.6
4	30	25	500	30%	OAC	TSL2591			7.1
						BH1750	0.27	0.28	10.7
						SI1145	0.30		10.7

necessitate additional calibration to ensure accuracy.

3.3. KPI analysis for DSFs

This section is dedicated to the results of experiment C, which investigates the KPIs of the DSF. The aim of presenting these results is to offer a thorough characterization of the DSF, as well as to evaluate the capabilities of the EcoDAQ system in facilitating such a comprehensive analysis.

It is well-known that airflow measurements in façade cavities are subject to substantial uncertainties, including those related to instrumentation and measurement procedures. The dynamic character of ventilation in confined spaces and the influence of various environmental factors are the sources of the complexity. A review of existing literature highlights several techniques, including anemometers [49], tracer gas methods [50], pressure differential sensors [51], ultrasonic flow meters [52], particle image velocimetry (PIV) [53], and laser doppler velocimetry (LDV) [54]. Each method has distinct advantages and limitations. Anemometers, regardless of type, are portable and responsive even at low speeds, but they can be prone to errors due to temperature drift and are relatively expensive. Tracer gas methods, commonly used for airflow rates, are simple to set up but suffer from high uncertainty due to uneven gas distribution and dynamic flow conditions. Ultrasonic flow measurement is non-intrusive and accurate, especially for higher velocities, but its performance diminishes at lower speeds. The pressure differential method is useful in mechanically ventilated façades, though it can be sensitive to environmental factors such as wind direction and speed fluctuations, reducing accuracy in natural airflow. Advanced techniques like PIV and LDV provide detailed, non-intrusive measurements of airflow patterns but are highly technical, expensive, and only suitable for laboratory conditions [55].

The measurement of airflow rate using inexpensive sensors is one of the obstacles that must be overcome in this experiment. Both the Sensirion SDP610 and SDP810 were used in this experiment to determine the pressure drop across the apertures. The opening is located in the lower portion of the window, and the height of the opening can be changed from 5 cm to 30 cm. An ultrasonic flow meter is installed inside the climate simulator close to the DSF. This meter records the flow rate of the fan that is placed to circulate air inside the cavity in a variety of different modes of window operation. There is a relationship between the pressure drop and the airflow rate, as shown by the equation $Q = a \times (\Delta P)^b$, which is derived from the orifice flow method [56]. Based on data from the ultrasonic flow meter and pressure drops acquired by the low-cost sensor SDP810, coefficients “a” and “b” were derived for different opening heights. For a 5 cm opening, the coefficients were $a = 353$ and $b = 0.515$. For a 15 cm opening, the coefficients were $a = 482$

and $b = 0.369$. For a 30 cm opening, the coefficients were $a = 647$ and $b = 0.891$. These results were derived using pressure drop values in hPa and airflow rates in m³/h. It was determined that the SDP810 sensor would be relied on for computations since the data that was acquired by the SDP610 displays greater variations. Both sensors provide almost identical means, however the SDP610 generates greater deviations from the mean value so the following calculations were decided to be based on SDP810 recordings.

Following the successful determination of the airflow rate coefficients through the DSF, Fig. 8 shows the results of the calculated KPIs for thirteen experiments, as outlined in Table 3. The first indicator, inside glazing surface temperature (KPI₁), is only depended on surface temperature sensors while other indicators are calculated using recordings of different types of sensors. Results from the two low-cost sensors (MCP9808 and TMP117) shows matching surface temperatures. The MAD from the reference value is 0.5 and 0.7 °C for TMP117 and MCP9808 respectively.

For the cavity airflow indicator, the average deviation from the reference values is 63 m³/h. Calculated coefficients “a” and “b”, which are based on the fan airflow rate, are used to determine the flow rate from the affordable SDP810 differential pressure sensor. Whereas the lab-grade velocity sensors placed in the cavity only display magnitude rather than direction, so it can be challenging to determine whether the mean value represents the true velocity.

In this study, the cavity heat loss is normalized per window surface area, adjusting measured values to a uniform per-unit-area basis. This standardization facilitates direct and meaningful comparisons with net heat flux values, ensuring consistent evaluation across different operation conditions and window systems. The third KPI, cavity heat loss or gain (q_{vent}), shows a significant variance of 13 W/m². This variance represents a substantial error of approximately 40 % when compared to the average measured value of 33 W/m². Such a notable discrepancy can be largely attributed to measurement errors associated with airflow rates. The divergence in readings between lab-grade and low-cost sensors could be a result of differences in measurement precision or the specific locations where these measurements were taken. In the case of lab-grade sensors, the approach involves using eight anemometers positioned at two different levels within the cavity, with the average of these readings representing the cavity’s airflow rate. Conversely, the methodology for low-cost sensors involves the use of differential pressure sensors, which are located at the bottom of the cavity near the opening. These sensors function by measuring the air pressure difference across the opening, offering a different perspective on airflow rate compared to the lab-grade anemometers. This variation in measurement techniques and sensor locations likely contributes to the observed discrepancies in calculating cavity heat loss or gain.

Fig. 8. MAD of calculated KPIs comparing lab-grade and EcoDAQ systems.

In relation to the net heat flux indication (q_{net}), the MAD values for all illuminance sensors range from 4.4 to 10.6 W/m², with the lowest values for TSL2591 (3.6 % error) and SI1145 (3.5 % error) and the highest for BH1750 (8.4 % error). For this indicator, the illumination sensors are utilized to monitor the transmitted incident solar radiation toward inside (I_{in}).

Fig. 9 presents a comprehensive overview of four KPIs across four different factors: ΔT , SI, FS, and OH. The KPIs are measured using both lab-grade sensors (shown in blue) and various low-cost sensors (shown in other colors).

The plot clearly indicates that KPI₁, which represents the indoor surface temperature, consistently rises with an increase in SI. This trend is evident across all sensor types, reinforcing the principle that solar gain is a primary determinant of indoor thermal conditions. The linearity of this response is a strong indication that, irrespective of the sensor quality, the effect of solar irradiance on surface temperature is unmistakable and quantifiable.

The lab-grade sensors indicate a positive correlation between ΔT and the cavity ventilation rate (KPI₂), which is consistent with the expected thermodynamic behavior where increased temperature difference from negative to positive values drive stronger upward directed airflow, superposing natural convection onto mechanical in this way. In contrast, measurements from low-cost sensors do not exhibit this trend, likely due to uncertainties in the calibration coefficients (a and b) in equation $Q = a \times (\Delta P)^b$. For both sensor types, an increase in FS results in a corresponding increase in airflow rate, as anticipated. However, OH appears to have a negligible effect on the airflow rate, indicating that within the tested range, OH is not a significant factor in driving ventilation within the cavity.

Upon examining the KPI₃ data from the plot, both the lab-grade and low-cost sensors follow similar trends in measuring cavity heat loss/gain. The uniform decrease in KPI₃ with rising ΔT from negative to positive values, as indicated by both sensor types, suggests the system response where the increased heat gain by the airflow occurs with negative temperature differences. Comparing to the influence of FS, it can be noticed that ΔT is a more critical factor in dictating heat transfer rates in the considered range of airflow rates. Conversely to ΔT , when SI increases, there is a corresponding steep rise in heat gain, suggesting that solar gain significantly affects the thermal dynamics of the cavity. Changes in FS and OH do not markedly alter the KPI₃, indicating that these factors may have a limited role in the thermal behavior within the observed range, or that the heat transfer is dominated by other factors not varying within these plots.

The plot for KPI₄ reveals a high degree of consistency between lab-grade and low-cost sensors, with a modest rise in net heat flux in response to rising ΔT and a pronounced surge with increased SI, underscoring solar irradiance as the predominant factor influencing the

net heat flux. The minimal variations in response to changes in FS and OH further confirm that these factors have a lesser impact on the KPI₄, showcasing the overriding effect of solar energy in the thermal dynamics captured by KPI₄, within the observed range of ventilation rates.

3.3.1. ANOVA

A Python script was developed to perform ANOVA using five components, and it was run for each of the four KPIs that were specified. The ANOVA analysis elucidates that ΔT and SI are the primary factors influencing KPI₁, KPI₃, and KPI₄ across both lab-grade and low-cost monitoring systems, indicating their integral role in driving the thermal performance of the double skin façade. This consistency across different sensor systems underscores the robustness of ΔT and SI as critical determinants of indoor surface temperature, cavity heat gain, and net heat flux. Conversely, for KPI₂, which measures airflow rate, FS emerges as the most significant factor in both systems. However, a notable divergence is observed between the types of sensors; while lab-grade sensors also point to a somewhat significant influence of ΔT on KPI₂, the outcomes from low-cost sensors do not demonstrate a statistically significant impact of ΔT , highlighting a potential discrepancy in sensitivity between the sensor types for this particular performance indicator.

To provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relative impacts of different factors on DSF performance, Fig. 10 has been included. The bar charts in this figure reveal the percentage contributions of each factor to the total variance observed in each KPI. This allows for a quick comparison of the variables' contributions across the different monitoring setups, thereby enhancing our interpretation of the complex interplay between environmental factors and DSF performance.

Results delineate that SI is the preeminent factor influencing KPI₁ and KPI₃, as demonstrated by its significant contribution to variance in both the lab-grade and EcoDAQ systems. Notably, for KPI₄, the contribution of SI factor stands out singularly, whereas the impact of ΔT is less pronounced, despite its statistical significance (p -values below the 0.05). This relative insignificance of ΔT for KPI₄ can be attributed to the extraordinarily low p -values associated with SI (lower by several magnitudes), suggesting an exponentially greater effect of SI on the net heat flux compared to ΔT .

With respect to KPI₂, the variance contribution from FS is particularly significant in the EcoDAQ system, highlighting its vital role in modulating airflow within the DSF cavity. Although ΔT is shown to influence variance in the lab-grade sensor data, its effect is less discernible in the EcoDAQ system measurements, potentially pointing to a sensitivity gap between the two types of sensors in capturing airflow dynamics.

The parallels drawn between the high-end and low-cost sensor systems in tracking essential DSF performance indicators reinforce the credibility of low-cost sensors for practical DSF applications, especially

Fig. 9. Factorial plot of KPIs: 1st row - Inside glazing surface temperature (KPI₁); 2nd row - Airflow rate in cavity (KPI₂); 3rd row - Normalized heat gain/loss rate through cavity (KPI₃); 4th row - Net heat flux through window (KPI₄).

for thermal-related metrics. The discrepancy observed in airflow measurement, however, underscores the need for further investigation to ensure measurement accuracy and further exploration to understand the underlying causes of such variances.

3.4. Challenges and limitations for real-world monitoring

This subsection discusses the main challenges and limits associated with the implementation of a long-term monitoring system for façade performance in real-world buildings in contrast to controlled laboratory conditions. It highlights practical considerations such as sensor installation, maintenance, durability, and the influence of occupant activities on environmental measurements.

Sensor installation and maintenance challenges: The installation and

maintenance of sensors in real buildings present challenges that do not arise in laboratory environments. The wiring must be carefully concealed to ensure that it does not obstruct aesthetics or functionality, while also allowing for maintenance access. Installing sensors in hard-to-reach areas, like façade cavities or external glazing, requires careful planning to avoid interfering with building operations. Environmental factors such as dust and moisture can also affect sensor performance over time, highlighting the need for durable designs and regular inspections to ensure reliability in dynamic real-world conditions.

Occupants and daily operations: In real-world buildings, environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, and CO₂ levels can be significantly influenced by occupants and daily activities. In contrast to controlled laboratory environments, human interactions, such as the adjustment of thermostats or the opening of windows, introduce

Fig. 10. Contribution of different factors to total variance of outcome variables (KPIs) recorded by lab-grade and EcoDAQ systems.

variables that influence sensor readings. Furthermore, sensors may be obstructed by furniture or interior elements, which can affect the movement of air and the accuracy of data. These factors must be considered when designing monitoring systems for reliable long-term data collection in occupied spaces.

Calibration and sensor drift: The long-term accuracy of environmental monitoring systems is contingent upon calibration and sensor drift. Sensor performance might decline over time as a result of environmental exposure, resulting in measurement drift. In real-world applications, periodic recalibration could be a solution to maintain data reliability, especially in long-term monitoring scenarios. The potential for sensor drift highlights the importance of bringing sensors back to the laboratory for performance verification after extended use in the field. Implementing redundancy measures, such as cross-referencing sensor data with lab-grade equipment, can help detect and correct deviations, ensuring consistent accuracy over time.

Considering these challenges, it is highly recommended to conduct

future field measurements by deploying the EcoDAQ system in operational buildings for long-term monitoring to validate its performance in real-world conditions. This will offer valuable insights into the system's reliability, accuracy, and adaptability outside controlled laboratory environments. The data collected will help evaluate the system's effectiveness in monitoring façade performance and environmental parameters influenced by occupants and dynamic building conditions. Furthermore, feedback from these field tests will guide design improvements, ensuring the system remains robust and suitable for long-term, practical use.

4. Conclusion

This study aimed to evaluate a EcoDAQ system against lab-grade sensors within a controlled climate simulator environment, focusing on the performance of advanced building envelopes. The primary research questions addressed were:

Q1. How can the EcoDAQ system capable of monitoring the performance of advanced building envelopes be developed?

The development process involved using a RPi with various low-cost solutions based on digital and, where digital is not available, analog sensors, to measure key environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, CO₂ levels, airflow rate, lighting, and heat flux. The system's architecture allowed for easy integration and flexible connectivity, providing comprehensive monitoring capabilities at a fraction of the cost of lab-grade systems. Real-time monitoring offers the possibility to enhance the system's functionality, by potentially enabling the detection of anomalies and long-term trends in a real building installation. Although fault-detection and assessment of performance degradation has not been directly investigated in this research, the sensitivity and reactivity of the proposed EcoDAQ demonstrates the suitability of such system for these tasks. Offering cost savings of approximately one-tenth compared to lab-grade systems, the EcoDAQ system proved to be a viable and cost-effective alternative for long-term environmental monitoring of advanced facade system.

Q2. Can the EcoDAQ system achieve the desired level of accuracy and sensitivity necessary for accurate and reliable monitoring?

Performance of the developed monitoring system was investigated in three phases. In the first phase (experiment A), the system's performance in reading single values for various thermo-physical parameters was promising. For most sensors, the system showed high accuracy in recording the average air temperature (< 0.5 °C), humidity (< 2.5 %), and surface temperature (< 0.9 °C), even without on-site calibration. However, calibration was found to be essential for precise measurements of some parameters, such as CO₂ and lighting levels.

In the second phase (experiment B), the system's performance for conventional parameter estimation demonstrated that U-value and g-value measurements from the low-cost system closely matched those from lab-grade sensors. The maximum discrepancies were 7% for U-value and 13% for g-value, underscoring the reliability of the low-cost system.

In the third phase (experiment C), the system's performance in representing the relationship between variables confirmed that performing an ANOVA with lab-grade data versus low-cost data yielded consistent results. Both DAQ systems identified SI and ΔT as significant factors affecting most presented DSF performance indicators. The ANOVA analysis demonstrated almost similar impact trends for independent factors on selected KPIs across both systems, validating the low-cost system's ability to accurately capture dependencies between independent and dependent variables.

In conclusion, the results confirm the suitability of the EcoDAQ system for advanced building envelope performance studies and broader applications in IEQ assessments. However, critical aspects such as the need for sensor calibration, particularly for CO₂ and lighting measurements, and variations in sensor sensitivity affecting airflow rate measurements, were detected. Future research should deploy the low-cost system in real-world settings to address these limitations and validate its reliability under dynamic environmental conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Behnam Rosti: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Aleksandar Jankovic:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Francesco Goia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Hans Martin Mathisen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Guangyu Cao:** Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The experimental dataset of this study is accessible on ZENODO, an open-access repository, available at [10.5281/zenodo.10651967](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10651967).

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